

Visual Active Exploration and Tracking: a Deep Reinforcement Learning Approach

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Abstract—Visual tracking approaches have recently gained significant attention from the research community. The majority of the state-of-the-art methods propose passive visual tracking solutions, *i.e.*, the camera cannot take actions to change its field of view in order to track the target. The objective of active approaches, instead, is to develop trackers capable of computing motion controls to maintain visual contact with the target. However, these strategies are still scarcely explored and most of those assume that the target to be within the tracker field of view at the beginning of the experiment. To remove this limitation, in this work we propose a novel deep reinforcement learning-based approach that is capable of exploring the surrounding environment, find the target and track it. We design and run different experiments to show the effectiveness of our approach and compare it with respect to current state-of-the-art (SotA) methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing interest in various robotics applications, such as autonomous driving, robot manipulation, and many others, encourages new research into the development of Visual Tracking (VT) systems. Despite the advances in the fields of Deep Learning and Computer Vision, in most works, these technologies have only been applied to *passive* tracking [1], [2]. This scenario is particularly limited since it assumes that the target to be tracked is always within the camera field-of-view (FoV).

To overcome this limitation, a recent line of research, focusing on Visual *Active* Tracking (VAT) [3], [4] is gaining increasing interest. In the active tracking scenario, the target is no longer constrained within the FoV; instead, it is necessary for the algorithm to dynamically adjust the position of the camera (or a mobile robot, as in our case), in order to maintain visual contact with it.

Although VAT can be addressed by combining a passive tracking module (*e.g.*, an object detector) with a separate one controlling the robot’s motion, much attention is shifting towards approaches based on end-to-end Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL). In fact, some recent works [3], [4] have shown that DRL can also be effectively applied to produce robust VAT algorithms.

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Fig. 1: Overview of the proposed *asymmetric* C-DNN architecture. The green blocks refer to the convolutional sub-branches, the yellow and light blue blocks indicate the fully connected and the GRU layers, respectively.

Despite the impressive results achieved, these approaches assume that the target is initially positioned within the tracker’s FoV. This assumption does not consider the case where the surroundings have first to be explored to discover the position of the target. Therefore, in our research, we propose *E-VAT*, an approach aimed to develop an active tracker that can explore a possibly unknown environment to find and track a specified target. Through different experiments, in simple, complex, and photo-realistic simulated environments, we show that our approach can effectively explore an unknown environment, find the target and track it. Furthermore, we demonstrate that despite our approach simultaneously solves two tasks, it matches and even outperforms the tracking performance of other SotA methods that, instead, have no exploration capabilities and make the simplifying assumption of having the target initially positioned in front of the tracker.

II. APPROACH AND TASK DETAILS

Given a specified possibly moving target, the goal of our approach is to explore the environment, detect the target and, once found, produce motion maneuvers to maintain it within its FoV by using only visual inputs. We define the tracker as an RL agent, which, by repeatedly interacting with an environment E , over a series of independent episodes and through discrete timesteps, receives input observations o_i , rewards r_i , and produces actions a_i .

Specifically, we assume that both tracker and target are free to move on a 2D plane. The tracker receives only the image stream from the front camera, and its action space is discrete. When an episode starts, the tracker and the target

are randomly placed in an unknown indoor environment, and until it ends, the tracker has to explore the scenario, find the target, and track it.

Following the recent works on DRL, we exploit Deep Neural Network (DNN) approximators and use the *actor-critic* formulation [3], [4]. Specifically, we aim to learn an *actor* model, which provides the optimal policy to fulfill the given task, and a *critic* model, which evaluates such a policy. The former acts only during the training phase, while the latter is the actual model used at test time to provide the action policies.

Contrary to the classical *symmetric actor-critic* implementations that require the two networks to share the same inputs, we adopt an asymmetric structure [5]. This strategy allows us to design the *Actor Network* to require only RGB inputs, while much more supervision information (that is more difficult to obtain at test time) can be exploited and provided to the *Critic Network* (as shown in Fig. 1).

In our setting, target tracking can only start after the tracker has explored the environment and found it. Therefore, an end-to-end optimization of the agent penalizes the tracking sub-task, leading to poor performance. To this aim, we design a new training algorithm that differs from the classical actor-critic framework for 3 main features:

a) *Sub-tasks decoupling and Agents splitting*: we divide the problem into two fully decoupled tasks. The former starts from a condition in which the *tracker* and the *target* are distant, and the goal is to explore the environment until the *target* is found. The latter begins with the *target* in front of the *tracker*, and the goal is to maintain the desired distance and angle between the *tracker* and the *target*.

b) *Actor with branches*: To also decouple the sub-tasks at the model level, the Actor Network is designed with two different branches, focusing on the exploration and tracking policy separately. During training, each branch update is computed by using trajectories collected by the respective agent group only (*i.e.*, exploration or tracking). At test time, the switching between the policies is handled by the *Target-Detection Network*, depending on whether it has detected the target or not.

c) *Critic with focused inputs*: since each branch only handles one sub-task, the critic must be able to discriminate between the tasks and judge the policies separately. To this aim, we forced the critic to focus only on a subset of inputs (the task-specific ones) by setting to zeros all the others.

The simulated environments used during the training phase are built by using the photo-realistic graphics engine Unreal Engine 4 (UE4)¹. The environment consists of a large unfurnished floor divided into rooms that are connected by corridors. At the start of each episode, the *tracker* is randomly spawned in a room of the floor, and, depending on whether it belongs to the exploration or tracking agent group, the *target* is randomly placed in a different room or in front of the *tracker*, respectively.

Since our model is trained in simulation only, we apply

¹<https://www.unrealengine.com>

TABLE I: RESULTS in DIFFERENT SCENARIOS

Scenario	Model	Target Found	Score Angle	Score Distance	Score Mean
Unfurnished	<i>E-VAT</i>	75%	0.66	0.88	0.77
	<i>AD-VAT+</i>	10%	0.63	0.74	0.69
	<i>AOT</i>	5%	0.93	0.78	0.86
Photo-realistic	<i>E-VAT</i>	40%	0.40	0.53	0.46
	<i>AD-VAT+</i>	10%	0.30	0.23	0.27
	<i>AOT</i>	10%	0.30	0.23	0.27

domain randomization [6] to achieve generalization also to more complex and photo-realistic contexts.

III. EXPERIMENTS

Experiments are designed to evaluate the ability of the agent to explore the environment, find the target, and keep it at the desired distance and at the center of the FoV.

Tests are performed both on simple scenarios, similar to those used for training and on more complex and photo-realistic contexts to evaluate the generalization capabilities of our model. The results reported in Table I show that our approach outperforms all the baselines with respect to the exploration metric. This result is a direct consequence of the learned exploration policy. Specifically, the model has learned the *wall-following* policy, which is optimal in environments with connected walls.

Considering the tracking task, our model shows better performance, or at least similar, with respect to all the baselines in the unfurnished environments. Furthermore, even if as expected we found a performance drop in the photo-realistic environment, our model achieves better results compared to the baselines in all metrics.

IV. FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The majority of the Visual Active Tracking systems only consider ground robots, active cameras or manipulators. In future work, we aim to extend this research also to the Micro Aerial Vehicles scenario, which is not trivial due to the complexity of the quadrotor dynamics and the extended action space dimension.

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